

DIGITAL PAYMENT ADOPTION, PURCHASE SELF-CONTROL, AND SOCIAL MEDIA: PREDICTORS OF FINANCIAL BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

The increasing integration of digital payment systems and social media platforms has reshaped how individuals manage everyday financial decisions. While these technologies enhance convenience and access, their implications for spending and saving behavior remain a growing concern, particularly among salaried employees. This study investigated the influence of digital payment adoption and social media influence on the financial behavior of 152 government employees, with purchase self-control examined as a mediating mechanism. Financial behavior was conceptualized in terms of wise spending and saving practices among employees in the Province of Bukidnon. Guided by a descriptive-correlational research design, the study gathered data from government employees using a validated survey instrument. Descriptive analysis, regression, and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) were employed to examine the variables and their relationships. Findings revealed generally high levels of digital payment adoption, social media influence, purchase self-control, and responsible financial behavior. Both digital payment adoption and social media influence were found to significantly affect financial behavior, while purchase self-control partially mediated these relationships. This indicates that although digital platforms influence financial decisions employee's ability to regulate spending plays an important role in maintaining responsible financial practices. These results are consistent with the Technology Acceptance Model, Theory of Planned Behavior, Behavioral Life-Cycle Hypothesis, and Social Learning Theory, emphasizing the combined roles of technology use, social influence, and self-regulation in shaping financial behavior. The study highlights the importance of strengthening purchase self-control to promote sustainable financial practices and long-term financial well-being.

Keywords: *Digital Payment Adoption, Purchase Self-control, Social Media Influence, Financial Behavior, Wise Spending, Saving Behavior*

INTRODUCTION

The adoption of digital payment systems is rapidly transforming financial transactions by making them faster, more convenient, and accessible. Digital Technologies such as mobile wallets, online banking, contactless payment applications have become integral to daily financial activities, particularly following COVID-19 pandemic, as institutions promoted cashless transactions to improve efficiency (World Bank, 2022). In the Philippines, digital payments now account for more than half of retail transactions reflecting the country's strong shift towards digital financial ecosystems (BSP, 2023). While these innovations enhance convenience, concerns have emerged regarding their influence on individuals' financial behavior, particularly in terms of wise spending and saving behavior.

Existing studies suggest that although digital payments improve efficiency, they may also encourage impulsive spending due to ease of use in transactions and reduced delay in payment processes (Afrizal, 2025). This effect is further intensified by social media influence, where individuals are exposed to consumer trends, peer comparisons, and persuasive marketing by content influencers (Pellegrino et al., 2022). In this context, purchase self-control plays a crucial role as a psychological mechanism that shapes financial decision-making. Prior research indicates that individuals with higher self-control are more likely to engage in wise spending and consistent saving behaviors (Davydenko et al., 2021; Lin, 2023).

Despite the growing body of literature, limited studies have examined the combined influence of digital payment adoption, social media, and purchase self-control on financial behavior, particularly among government employees in local settings. Anchored by TAM Theory, Theory of Planned Behavior, social learning theory and Behavioral Life-cycle hypothesis, this study addresses this gap by examining the mediating role of purchase self-control in the relationship between digital payment adoption, social media influence, and financial behavior, specifically in terms of wise spending and saving behavior. The findings aim to provide evidence-based insights that can support financial literacy initiatives, promote responsible digital payment usage, and enhance financial well-being among employees in the public sector.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is participants' assessment in their digital payment adoption in terms of:
 - 1.1 Perceived usefulness
 - 1.2 Ease of use?
2. What is the participants' assessment of their purchase self-control?

3. What is the participants' assessment of social media influence?
4. What is the participants' assessment of their financial behavior in terms of
 - 4.1 Wise Spending and
 - 4.2 Saving Behavior?
5. Do digital payment adoption and social media predict financial behavior?
6. Is there a mediating effect of the participants' self-control on the influence of digital payment adoption and social media on their financial behavior?

METHODOLOGY

For the objectives of this study, which focused on examining the mediating role of purchase self-control in the relationship between digital payment adoption, social media influence, and financial behavior, a causal descriptive-correlational research design was used. This design was appropriate because it not only described the relationships among the variables but also explored how digital payment adoption and social media influence affect financial behavior through purchase self-control. Instead of simply identifying associations, the study aimed to understand how these variables interact and contribute to changes in financial behavior. A quantitative approach was applied to measure participants' perceptions without manipulating any variables, allowing the researcher to observe natural relationships among the constructs.

The participants of the study were government employees from a selected municipality in the province of Bukidnon, with an estimated population of 244. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 152 respondents was determined, which is also consistent with recommended sample sizes for correlational research and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) (Hair et al., 2022). These participants included regular, contractual, and job order employees who had experience using digital payment platforms and were active on social media.

To ensure that the data gathered were relevant, only employees who met specific criteria were included. Participants had to be currently employed and have experience using digital payment systems and social media platforms. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained before data collection. A simple random sampling method was used, giving all eligible employees an equal chance of being selected. A list of employees was obtained from the municipal office, and respondents were chosen through a random selection process. This method helped reduce bias and improved the reliability and generalizability of the findings.

Data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire and analyzed using IBM SPSS and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). For Research Problems 1 to 4, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to describe the participants' responses and assess the levels of digital payment adoption, purchase self-control, social media influence, and financial behavior. For Research Problem 5, multiple regression analysis was applied to determine how digital payment adoption and social media influence predict financial behavior, particularly in

terms of wise spending and saving. This helped identify the contribution of each independent variable in explaining financial behavior. For Research Problem 6, mediation analysis using SEM was conducted to examine the role of purchase self-control in linking digital payment adoption and social media influence to financial behavior. The model was evaluated using standard goodness-of-fit indices such as CMIN/DF, CFI, TLI, NFI, and RMSEA. SEM was chosen because it allows the analysis of both direct and indirect effects within a single model. All statistical tests were conducted at a 0.05 level of significance to ensure the reliability of the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the summary of digital payment adoption across its two dimensions, showing a generally High interpretation among participants, with an overall mean of 4.23 and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.6, indicating a strong consistency in participants' perceptions. Among the dimensions, perceived usefulness obtained the highest mean score of 4.27 suggesting that participants generally value the efficiency, convenience and practicality of digital payment systems in managing financial transactions. This observation is supported by studies of (Yang et al., 2021) emphasizing that perceived usefulness and remains a key determinant of technology adoption, as users are more likely to utilized digital systems that enhance performance and productivity.

Table 1
Summary table of Digital Payment Adoption

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Perceived usefulness	4.27	High	0.71
Ease of use	4.18	High	0.68
Digital payment adoption	4.23	High	0.64

Meanwhile, ease of use also recorded as generally high with a mean score of 4.18, indicating that participants find digital payment platforms as simple, intuitive, and easy to navigate. This aligns with the findings of Judijanto & Wardhani (2024) that user-friendly interfaces, clear instructions, and minimal complexity contribute to higher satisfaction and continued usage of digital financial technologies. Overall, the results suggest that the strong adoption of digital payments is driven by both functional benefits and ease of operation, reinforcing their role as a widely accepted and reliable tool in everyday financial activities.

Table 2 indicates a generally high overall mean level of purchase self-control (M = 4.06) with a standard deviation of 0.73, suggesting that participants demonstrate disciplined and consistent spending behavior. Most participants generally rated their purchase self-control as High (44.74%) and very high (31.58%), while a smaller proportion perceived it as moderate (21.76%) or low (1.97%). These findings imply that participants are generally capable of managing their spending despite the convenience of digital payments and

exposure to social media influences, consistent with the studies emphasizing the role of self-control in reducing impulsive consumption (Davydenko et al., 2021)

Among the indicators, "I avoid making impulsive purchases" recorded the highest mean score ($M = 4.10$) with a standard deviation of 0.87, highlighting participants' ability to resist unplanned or emotionally driven spending. This finding aligns with previous research by Moser, (2020) indicating that individuals with higher self-control are less prone to impulsive buying, particularly in online or digital contexts.

In contrast, "I follow a set budget when I shop" obtained the lowest mean score of 4.02 with standard deviation of 0.86, although it still falls within the high interpretation. This indicates that while participants are generally capable of avoiding impulsive purchases, consistently adhering to a fixed budget may present greater challenges. This observation is supported by the study of Skwara & Wienert, (2024) noting that maintaining strict budgeting discipline remains a common difficulty despite strong self-control in other financial behaviors.

Overall, the results confirms that participants exhibit strong purchase self-control, particularly in resisting impulsive spending, although maintaining consistent budget adherence may require further reinforcement. These findings highlight the importance of strengthening budgeting practices alongside self-control to support more sustainable financial behavior.

Table 2
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of their Purchase Self-control

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage	
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	48	31.58	
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	68	44.74	
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate	33	21.71	
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	3	1.97	
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	0	0.00	
Total			152	100.0	
Overall Mean			4.06		
Interpretation			High		
SD			0.73		
Specific Indicators			Mean	Description	SD
1 I follow a set budget when I shop.			4.02	Agree	0.86
2 I avoid making impulsive purchases.			4.10	Agree	0.87
3 I maintain control over my spending habits.			4.05	Agree	0.76

Table 3 indicates a generally high overall level of social media influence with a mean of 4.09 and a standard deviation of 0.67, suggesting that participants experience a strong and consistent exposure to financial content, digital payment promotions, and purchasing

trends through social media platforms. Most participants generally rated social media influence as High (47.71%) or very High (32.24%), while a smaller proportion assessed it as moderate (21.05%), with no responses in the low or very low categories, reflecting a widely shared perception of its significant influence. These findings is consistent with the studies highlighting its role in influencing consumer decisions and financial technology adoption (Madi, 2025, Shvaher et al., 2021)

Among the indicators “I frequently see digital payment promotions on social media” recorded as the highest mean of 4.30 with a standard deviation of 0.79, indicating that participants are consistently exposed to digital payment-related advertisements. This reflects the pervasive nature of targeted social media marketing which increases awareness and familiarity with financial services (Sharma, 2024).

In contrast, “I learn about financial tools and strategies by following social media content” obtained the lowest mean of 3.97 with a standard deviation of 0.83, though it still falls within the high interpretation. This was supported by the study of Tiwari and Tiwari (2020) which states that the effectiveness of social media as a learning tool depends on user’s digital literacy and content preferences.

Overall, the results confirm that social media significantly influences financial exposure and awareness although its role as a primary source of financial learning varies among the adoption of every individual.

Table 3
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of Social Media Influence

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage	
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	49	32.24	
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	71	46.71	
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate	32	21.05	
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	0	0.00	
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	0	0.00	
Total			152	100.0	
Overall Mean			4.09		
Interpretation			High		
SD			0.67		
Specific Indicators			M	Description	SD
1	I frequently see digital payment promotions on social media.		4.30	Agree	0.79
2	I often buy items that are promoted through social media channels.		4.00	Agree	0.88
3	I learn about financial tools and strategies by following social media content.		3.97	Agree	0.83

Table 4 indicates a generally high overall level of financial behavior across two dimensions, with wise spending and saving behavior both interpreted as High. Among the dimensions, wise spending obtained the highest mean of 4.16 with a standard deviation of 0.63, suggesting that participants consistently demonstrate prudent and well-evaluated spending practices. This finding supported by the study of Dahal, (2024) which reflects a tendency to prioritize needs, assess purchases carefully, and manage expenses responsibly, which are essential for maintaining financial stability.

In contrast, saving behavior recorded a slightly lower mean of 3.96 with a standard deviation of 0.76, though it still falls within high interpretation. This indicates that while participants generally engage in saving practices, there is greater variability in consistency compared to spending behavior. Existing literature explains that saving requires sustained discipline and long-term planning, making it more sensitive to individual and situational factors (Despard et al., 2020; Dahal, 2024)

Overall, the results confirm that participants exhibit sound financial behavior, with stronger consistency in wise spending than in saving practices, highlighting the importance of reinforcing regular saving habits to support long-term financial well-being.

Table 4
Summary table of Financial Behavior

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Wise spending	4.16	High	0.63
Saving behavior	3.96	High	0.76
Financial behavior	4.06	High	0.61

Table 5 presents the results of a multiple regression analysis examining whether digital payment adoption and social media influence significantly predict financial behavior among participants. The model indicates a significant overall fit ($R^2 = 0.184$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that approximately 18.4% of the variance in financial behavior is explained by the combined influence of the predictors. Hence, H_01 , which states that digital payment adoption and social media influence do not significantly predict financial behavior, is rejected. This finding aligns with Putrevu and Mertzanis, (2024), who emphasized that digital payment adoption enhances convenience, transaction efficiency, and financial discipline. Additionally, Estelami and Florendo (2021), and Yanto et al. (2021) found that social media exposure not only informs participants about financial opportunities but also promotes responsible financial behaviors through peer benchmarking and online financial education.

Among the predictors, digital payment adoption showed a positive and statistically significant effect ($\beta = 0.231$, $p = 0.004$), indicating that higher levels of adoption are associated with improved financial behavior. This suggests that individuals who actively use digital payment tools tend to demonstrate better financial management practices. Accordingly, H_02 is rejected. This finding is consistent with studies highlighting the role of

digital payment systems in enhancing financial efficiency and discipline (Putrevu & Mertzanis, 2024).

Table 5
Regression Analysis of the Participants' Assessment of Digital Payment Adoption, and Social media Influence on Financial Behavior

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	2.016	.359		5.614	.000
Digital payment adoption	.220**	.074	.231	2.956	.004
Social media influence	.273**	.072	.296	3.800	.000
Model Summary					
R = 0.429	R ² = 0.184	Adj. R ² = 0.173	F = 16.815**	p = .000	

**significant at 0.01 level

*significant at 0.05 level

Social media influence also significantly predicts financial behavior ($\beta = 0.296$, $p < 0.001$), with a slightly stronger effect compared to digital payment adoption. This indicates that increased exposure to financial content and peer interactions on social media is associated with better financial decision-making. Thus, Ho3 is rejected. This supports existing literature emphasizing social media as a platform for financial awareness, peer learning, and behavioral influence (Estelami & Florendo, 2021; Yanto et al., 2021).

Overall, the results confirm that both digital payment adoption and social media influence are significant predictors of financial behavior, with social media exerting a relatively stronger effect. These findings highlight the importance of leveraging digital platforms not only for convenience but also as tools for promoting responsible financial practices.

Table 6 present the model fit indices used to evaluate the adequacy of the structural model testing the mediating effect of self-control on the influence of social media and digital payment adoption on financial behavior. The SRMR value of 0.08 meets the standard criterion of ≤ 0.08 , indicating that the fit is acceptable between the predicted and observed correlations. Both d_{ULS} (1.605) and d_G (0.687) show that the estimated model values are equal to the saturated model values, demonstrating that the structural model closely approximates the ideal model.

Finally, the NFI value of 0.71 falls within the acceptable range (≥ 0.70), further confirming that the model achieves an adequate level of fit. Overall, these indices collectively suggest that the proposed model is acceptable for testing the hypothesized mediating effect of self-control.

Table 6
Model Fit Indices for Testing the Mediating Effect of Self-Control on the Influence of Digital Payment Adoption and Social Media on Financial Behavior

Fit Index	Standard Criteria	Saturated Model	Estimated Model	Interpretation
SRMR	≤ 0.08	0.08	0.08	Acceptable
d_ ULS	Estimated ≤ Saturated	1.605	1.605	Acceptable
d_ G	Estimated ≤ Saturated	0.687	0.687	Acceptable
NFI	≥ 0.90 (ideal), ≥ acceptable	0.70	0.71	Acceptable

Figure 1 shows the path analysis shows that the model explains 29.3% of the variance in financial behavior, indicating a weak to moderate level of explanatory power. The direct effects of digital payment adoption ($\beta = 0.037$) and social media influence ($\beta = 0.014$) on financial behavior are minimal. However, both variables demonstrate stronger indirect effects through purchase self-control, with coefficients of $\beta = 0.101$ and $\beta = 0.174$, respectively.

The path from purchase self-control to financial behavior is significant, confirming its role as a key mediating variable. These results suggest that while digital payment usage and social media exposure alone have limited direct influence, they contribute to improved financial behavior by enhancing individuals' ability to regulate spending and make disciplined financial decisions.

Figure 1. Path Analysis of the Mediating Effect of Purchase Self-control on the Relationship between Digital payment adoption, Social media influence, and Financial Behavior.

Table 7 presents the mediation analysis of purchase self-control on the effects of digital payment adoption and social media influence on financial behavior. The results indicate that digital payment adoption has significant total effect on financial behavior ($B = 0.253$, $p = .006$), with a direct effect ($B = 0.179$) and a significant indirect effect through purchase self-control ($B = 0.074$, $p = .010$). This implies that while digital payment adoption contributes to financial behavior, its effect is partly explained by individuals' ability to regulate their spending, consistent with the study of (Bai, 2023; Hernandez-Perez & Rambaud, 2025) highlighting the mediating role of self-control in financial decision-making.

For social media influence, the total effect on financial behavior is also significant ($B = 0.294$, $p = .001$), with both a significant direct effect ($B = 0.197$, $p = .014$) and indirect effect through purchase self-control ($B = 0.098$, $p = .013$). This likewise indicates partial mediation, meaning that self-control explains part of the relationship while other factors also contribute. This finding suggests that exposure to social media shapes financial behavior, but its impact is strengthened when individuals exercise greater self-control, supporting existing research on mediated financial behaviors (Saripah et al., 2024; Hernandez-Perez & Rambaud, 2025)

These findings confirms that purchase self-control explains part of the relationship between both predictors and financial behavior, while other factors may also contribute. Accordingly, the null hypothesis (H_04), which states that there is no mediating effect of purchase self-control on the influence of digital payment adoption and social media on financial behavior, is rejected.

Overall, the results confirm that purchase self-control plays a significant mediating role, though with modest effect sizes. It highlights that financial behavior is not solely driven by digital tools and social media exposure, but largely depends on individuals' capacity for self-regulation. Strengthening self-control mechanisms is therefore essential in promoting responsible financial behavior in digital environments.

Table 7
Mediation Analysis Summary of the effect of the Participants' Self-control on the influence of Digital Payment Adoption and Social Media on their Financial Behavior

Predictor→Outcome			Effect Type	B	SE	β	Z	p
Digital Adoption →	Purchase Self-Control →	Financial Behavior	Total Effect	0.253	0.091	0.253	2.772	0.006
			Direct Effect	0.179	0.086	0.179	2.091	0.037
			Indirect Effect	0.074	0.029	0.074	2.560	0.010

Social Media Influence →	Total Effect	0.294	0.079	0.294	3.706	0.000
Purchase Self-Control →	Direct Effect	0.197	0.080	0.197	2.460	0.014
Financial Behavior	Indirect effect	0.098	0.039	0.099	2.480	0.013

Note. *Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Conclusions

The study revealed that digital payment adoption and social media influence are key components of the modern financial environment, shaping how individuals make financial decisions. The high acceptance of digital payment systems reflects their value in enhancing efficiency and convenience, consistent with the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989), which highlights perceived usefulness and ease of use as primary drivers of adoption. However, while these technologies support financial management, they also present behavioral challenges that require proper regulation.

Social media further plays a significant role in shaping financial awareness and consumption patterns through exposure to online content, peer behavior, and marketing influences. This aligns with Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977), emphasizing that financial behavior is influenced not only by individual choices but also by social and digital environments.

The study also highlights purchase self-control as a crucial mechanism in managing financial behavior. Consistent with the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and the Behavioral Life-Cycle Hypothesis, financial outcomes depend largely on individuals' ability to regulate impulses and make disciplined decisions. The mediating role of self-control confirms that digital tools and social media influence financial behavior indirectly by shaping individuals' capacity for self-regulation.

Overall, achieving sound financial behavior in the digital context requires a balance between technology use and behavioral control. The study contributes to existing knowledge by establishing the mediating role of purchase self-control, emphasizing that responsible financial behavior depends not only on access to technology but also on individuals' ability to manage their financial decisions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to promote responsible digital payment adoption, guided social media use, enhanced purchase self-control, and sound financial decision-making:

1. Local Government Units (LGUs) may collaboratively implement financial literacy programs focusing on budgeting, saving, debt management, and responsible digital

payment use. Promoting digital tools such as spending limits and expense trackers, along with awareness campaigns on evaluating social media content, can help strengthen self-control and reduce impulsive spending. Integrating self-regulation and goal-setting strategies in training programs may further enhance financial discipline.

2. Financial Institutions and Government Agencies may develop workplace financial well-being programs, such as savings schemes, financial counseling, and incentive-based initiatives, to encourage long-term financial security and responsible financial behavior.

3. Teachers, Instructors, and Educational Institutions may integrate critical consumption and self-control training into media literacy and financial education. Emphasizing responsible digital spending and evaluation of online financial content can help develop informed and disciplined financial decision-making among learners.

4. Future Researchers may expand this research by including additional variables such as financial literacy, income, and psychological factors, and by using qualitative or mixed methods to gain deeper insights, particularly in rural or underserved contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards guided by the Belmont Report principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were also given the freedom to withdraw at any time without consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of respondents were strictly maintained, and all data were handled in accordance with Data Privacy regulations and used solely for research purposes. Participants' well-being was safeguarded throughout the study.

The researchers declare that there is no conflict of interest, and plagiarism was strictly avoided with all sources properly cited. The interpretation of findings was conducted objectively, without bias. Furthermore, the use of artificial intelligence tools was limited to assistance in idea generation and language refinement, with all outputs carefully reviewed to ensure accuracy, transparency, and ethical compliance.

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